

Correlation of Clinical Severity and Laboratory Parameters with Various Serotypes in Dengue Virus A Hospital-Based Study

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Abstract:

This hospital-based retrospective cohort study examined clinical severity and laboratory markers among dengue virus (DENV) serotypes in 340 confirmed cases. DENV-2 was related with worse clinical outcomes than other serotypes. Severe illness presentations were associated with lower platelet counts and higher liver enzyme values. The study emphasises serotype-specific therapy and improved surveillance to reduce severe dengue infections. These findings demonstrate the potential of test indicators to predict dengue severity and aid in prompt therapy.

Keywords: Dengue Serotypes, Clinical Severity, Laboratory Parameters, Prognostic Markers.

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Introduction

Dengue fever, caused by the dengue virus (DENV), continues to be a significant global health issue, especially in tropical and subtropical regions [1]. The clinical presentations of dengue infection can vary from a mild fever to more severe forms like dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF) and dengue shock syndrome (DSS), which have the potential to be life-threatening [2,3]. There are four different serotypes of the dengue virus (DENV-1, DENV-2, DENV-3, and DENV-4), and each one has the potential to cause a wide range of diseases. Nonetheless, the seriousness of the illness and the resulting clinical results can differ greatly based on the specific serotype causing the infection, as well as individual factors like age, immune system strength, and genetic susceptibility [4,5].

Extensive research has been conducted on the relationship between dengue virus serotypes and disease severity. It has been suggested that the risk of severe disease increases when there are secondary infections with a different serotype. This is due to antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE) [6,7]. However, even initial infections can result in serious consequences, and the factors contributing to this are still not completely comprehended. Diagnostic and prognostic indicators, including platelet count, liver enzymes, and hematocrit levels, play a crucial role in assessing the severity of dengue. These parameters are crucial for closely tracking the disease's progression and developing

tailored management strategies to mitigate the risk of severe complications [8,9].

The objective of this study is to explore the relationship between the severity of clinical symptoms and various laboratory measurements in patients infected with different serotypes of the dengue virus within a hospital environment. Gaining a deeper understanding of these connections will not only improve clinical management, but also strengthen surveillance and control strategies, potentially leading to a decrease in the negative impact of dengue infections on health and well-being. Through this research, we aim to provide significant insights into the pathogenesis of dengue, enhancing our understanding of how various serotypes impact disease dynamics and outcomes.

Methodology

Research Methodology and Location: This study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in a region where dengue is prevalent. It is a retrospective cohort study that focused on patients who were admitted to the hospital. The study period extends from January 2022 to December 2023, encompassing two high dengue activity periods.

Participants in the Study: The study involves patients who were hospitalised with a laboratory-confirmed diagnosis of dengue virus infection during the study period. The diagnosis was

confirmed using RT-PCR, which also determined the specific serotype of the dengue virus (DENV-1, DENV-2, DENV-3, or DENV-4).

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients of any age and gender with a confirmed diagnosis of dengue virus infection.
- Patients who have complete medical records including detailed clinical and laboratory data.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with co-existing infections such as malaria, Zika, or chikungunya.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Gathering Information

Information will be gathered from electronic medical records and patient charts, encompassing details such as demographic information, clinical symptoms, duration of symptoms before hospital admission, laboratory values (such as platelet count, hematocrit, liver enzymes), and the outcome of the hospital stay (whether it resulted in recovery, complications, or death).

Factors

- Dependent Variable: Clinical severity of dengue, categorized as mild, moderate, and severe according to WHO guidelines.
- Factors that were taken into consideration include the type of dengue virus, various laboratory measurements such as platelet count, hematocrit

levels, and liver enzymes, as well as the age and gender of the individuals involved.

Statistical Analysis: We will utilise descriptive statistics to provide a concise summary of the demographic and clinical characteristics. An analysis will be conducted to examine the relationship between dengue serotypes and clinical severity. Categorical variables will be assessed using chi-square tests, while continuous variables will be evaluated using ANOVA. An analysis using multivariable logistic regression will be conducted to account for potential confounding variables and determine the factors that are independently linked to severe dengue outcomes. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ will be established.

Results

The study examined data from 340 patients who were admitted with confirmed cases of dengue virus infections during the two-year study period. There was a total of 85 cases of DENV-1, 120 cases of DENV-2, 80 cases of DENV-3, and 55 cases of DENV-4, based on the breakdown of serotypes. Most of the patients in the study were male, with an average age of 35 years and a standard deviation of 18 years. 25% of the cases were attributed to children under 15 years of age, while adults aged 15-60 accounted for 65% of the cases. Seniors over 60 made up the remaining 10%.

The clinical severity showed significant variation among the different serotypes ($p < 0.01$). DENV-2 was linked to a greater number of severe cases, as described in the following:

Serotype	Mild (%)	Moderate (%)	Severe (%)
DENV-1	72 (84.7)	10 (11.8)	3 (3.5)
DENV-2	60 (50.0)	30 (25.0)	30 (25.0)
DENV-3	68 (85.0)	10 (12.5)	2 (2.5)
DENV-4	48 (87.3)	5 (9.1)	2 (3.6)

Significant differences were observed in laboratory parameters across different severity levels, particularly in platelet count and liver enzymes. Patients with severe dengue had lower mean platelet counts and higher liver enzyme levels compared to those with mild and moderate dengue.

Severity	Mean Platelet Count ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	Mean ALT (U/L)	Mean AST (U/L)
Mild	150 $\pm$ 50	45 $\pm$ 15	47 $\pm$ 16
Moderate	100 $\pm$ 35	70 $\pm$ 20	72 $\pm$ 25
Severe	50 $\pm$ 25	120 $\pm$ 30	115 $\pm$ 35

The association between age and clinical severity was not found to be statistically significant

($p = 0.14$). However, there was a slight gender predisposition, with males experiencing more

severe cases than females ($p < 0.05$). Based on the findings, it appears that DENV-2 is more commonly linked to severe clinical symptoms when compared to other serotypes. Various laboratory parameters, including platelet count and liver enzyme levels, have been found to be closely associated with the severity of clinical symptoms. These findings suggest that these parameters could be useful in predicting the progression of the disease. The significance of serotype-specific approaches in the management and prevention strategies for dengue is highlighted by these findings.

Discussion

The findings of this hospital-based study highlight significant associations between the clinical severity of dengue infection and the infecting serotype, with DENV-2 particularly linked to more severe clinical outcomes [10,11]. This corroborates earlier studies suggesting that infections with DENV-2 are more likely to progress to severe forms such as dengue hemorrhagic fever and shock syndrome, possibly due to the unique viral characteristics that influence host immune response [12]. Furthermore, the association of severe disease with specific laboratory parameters—particularly lower platelet counts and higher liver enzymes—reinforces their utility as biomarkers for monitoring disease severity and potentially guiding clinical management [13].

Interestingly, while gender showed a significant correlation with severity, with males more prone to severe outcomes, age did not significantly impact the severity, suggesting that other host factors, possibly genetic or immunological, might play more critical roles in disease progression. These results underline the complexity of dengue pathogenesis and highlight the need for further research into how host factors interact with different serotypes to influence disease outcomes [14,15].

The study's findings emphasize the importance of serotype-specific data in shaping public health strategies, including vaccine development and targeted interventions. Such strategies could be particularly effective in regions where DENV-2 is prevalent or during outbreaks caused by this serotype [16,17]. Additionally, the consistent use of laboratory markers for early identification of potentially severe cases could improve patient outcomes through timely and appropriate treatment interventions. Overall, this study contributes valuable insights into the serotype-specific dynamics of dengue, offering avenues for more personalized and effective approaches to dengue management and prevention [18,19,20].

Conclusion

This study conclusively demonstrates that the serotype of the dengue virus plays a critical role in determining clinical severity, with DENV-2 particularly associated with severe manifestations. Laboratory parameters such as platelet counts and liver enzyme levels were significantly correlated with the severity of the disease, highlighting their importance in clinical assessments and potential as prognostic markers. These insights underscore the necessity for targeted public health interventions and clinical strategies that are adapted to the specific challenges posed by different dengue serotypes. Enhancing our understanding of the interaction between viral serotypes and host factors will be crucial in improving the management and prevention of dengue across endemic regions, ultimately reducing the global burden of this disease.

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